

EELV Secondary Payload Adapter (ESPA): Providing Increased Access to Space¹

Peter M. Wegner and Jeff Ganley
Air Force Research Laboratory Space Vehicles Directorate (AFRL/VS)
3550 Aberdeen Ave SE, Bldg 472
Kirtland AFB, NM 87117-5776
505-853-3486
wegnerp@vs.af.mil

Joseph R. Maly
CSA Engineering
2565 Leghorn Street
Mountain View, CA
650-210-9000
jmaly@csaengineering.com

Abstract—There currently exist few options for small satellites and space experiments needing access to space. Therefore, many small satellites wait years for access to space. At the same time, many expendable launch vehicles are flown every year with unused payload margin. The EELV Secondary Payload Adapter (ESPA) is designed to take advantage of this unused payload margin to deploy up to six 181 kg (400 lb) secondary payloads. ESPA consists of an aluminum cylinder with six standardized secondary payload (SPL) mounting locations. The fore and aft flanges on the ESPA ring duplicate the 157.5 cm (62.01 in) EELV Standard Interface Plane, making ESPA transparent to the primary payload. By taking advantage of existing unused payload margin, ESPA will increase access to space for small satellites and space experiments.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AFRL/VSSV – Air Force Research Laboratory,
Spacecraft Technologies Branch
CG – Center of Gravity
FEM – Finite Element Modeling

ESPA – EELV Secondary Payload Adapter
EELV – Evolved Expendable Launch Vehicle
PPL – Primary Payload
SPL – Secondary Payload
SIP – Standard Interface Plane

1. INTRODUCTION

The Air Force's Space Test Program (STP), managed under SMC/TE provides spaceflight for qualified DOD sponsored experiments at no charge to the experimenter, via the DOD-Space Experiments Review Board (DOD-SERB). STP currently has a number of small DOD payloads needing access to space. These include XSS-10, XSS-11, Sapphire, PCSAT, and the TechSat21 constellation. However, there currently exist few options for small satellites and space experiments needing access to space. A dedicated launch vehicle is often prohibitively expensive and the U.S. does not have a well-developed capability to launch satellites as Secondary Payloads (SPL). To meet this growing need, STP in 1995 identified large unused payload margins on the majority of the DOD's EELV (Evolved Expendable Launch Vehicle) manifests. In some cases this unused payload margin is as much as 3628 kg (8000 lb). At that time STP advocated utilizing this excess payload margin to deploy secondary payloads.

Other groups have also advocated the use of unused payload margin to deploy small satellites and space experiments as secondary payloads. In 1996 the University Space Research Association (USRA)

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expressed interest in utilizing excess payload capacity on US launch vehicles to fly university experiments as SPLs. NASA has also expressed interest in using excess capacity on Air Force launch vehicles to deploy constellations of small secondary satellites. The French Space Agency, CNES, developed a secondary payload accommodation system known as the ASAP ring, for the Ariane IV launch vehicle. The ring allows up to six micro- or mini-satellites to be deployed after reaching the primary orbit. A 50 kg (110 lb) satellite can be launched for \$300K - \$1000K.

To meet the needs of small satellites and space experiments, SMC/TE's Space Test Program Office and the Air Force Research Laboratory's Space Vehicles Directorate (AFRL/VS) have joined together to develop the EELV Secondary Payload Adapter (ESPA). ESPA is designed to take advantage of the large amount of unused payload margin on the EELV to deploy up to six 181 kg (400 lb) secondary payloads. By taking advantage of existing unused payload margin, ESPA will increase access to space for small satellites and space experiments.

2. ESPA CONFIGURATION

ESPA consists of 1.5-inch thick, 7075 aluminum cylinder with six standardized secondary payload (SPL) mounting flanges, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. ESPA Cylinder Showing Primary and Secondary Payload Mounting Flanges

The ESPA cylinder is 61 cm (24 in) tall from the bottom of the lower flange to the top of the upper flange. Therefore, ESPA raises the primary payload by a total of 24-inches. With the optional primary payload isolation system in place between ESPA and the primary payload, the primary payload is lifted an additional 15 cm (6 in) for a total change in height of 76 cm (30 in). In order to accommodate this change in height, the ESPA structure is designed to be very stiff in all directions. This approach minimizes the effect of this increase in height on the rocking frequency of the PPL.

Two competing contractors are developing the EELV: Lockheed Martin is building the Atlas V launch vehicle and Boeing is developing the Delta IV launch vehicle. ESPA is designed for use on either LV. This is achieved by using the 157.7 cm (62.01 in) EELV Standard Interface Plane (SIP) on both the fore and aft end of the ESPA cylinder. Therefore, on the Boeing Delta IV launch vehicle ESPA connects between the Delta IV conical adapter and the primary payload; whereas on Lockheed Martin's Atlas IV vehicle ESPA will connect between the Cylindrical C1 or C2 adapter and the primary payload. By using the EELV 157.5 cm (62.01 in) standard interface plane, and designing ESPA to be as stiff as possible in all directions, ESPA is nearly transparent to the primary payload. A computer model of ESPA shown on the launch vehicle stack is shown in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2 ESPA on the Launch Vehicle Stack

Each of the mounting flanges has 24 equally spaced bolts on a 38 cm (15 in) diameter ring. There is a space of 2.5 cm (1 in) between the outer wall of the ESPA cylinder and the inner face of the SPL mounting flange to allow access for a wrench or fingers to tighten the SPL fasteners. The SPL flanges will have through holes to accommodate a bolt and nut connection. The secondary payload interface is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Secondary Payload Mounting Flange

Figure 4 Secondary Payload Static Volume and C.G. Envelopes

3. ESPA DESIGN REQUIREMENTS

ESPA is designed to carry six 181 kg (400 lb) SPLs that fit within a dynamic envelope of 61 cm x 61 cm x 97 cm (24 in x 24 in x 38-in). However, it should be noted that the interior of the SPL Mounting Flanges is entirely open. Thus, it would be possible for the SPL to protrude through the 13.20-inch opening into the interior of the ESPA cylinder. If this extra volume is utilized, tip-off during deployment of the SPLs must be eliminated.

ESPA is designed for SPLs in which the CG for the SPLs fits within a 50.8 cm (20 in) tall by 1.3 cm (0.5 in) cylinder as measured from the end of the ESPA SPL Mounting Flange. This tight control of the SPL CG will allow the ESPA ring to be easily mass balanced. This configuration is shown in Figure 4.

ESPA is designed for use with Primary Payloads (PPLs) having a maximum mass of 6800 kg (15,000 lb). The PPLs can have a maximum CG of 305 cm (120 in) measured from the bottom of the lower flange of the ESPA cylinder. ESPA is transparent to the PPL in that it mimics the EELV 157.5 cm (62.01 in) Standard Interface Plane.

ESPA is designed to quasi-static acceleration load factors that were derived from the EELV Standard Interface Specification Document (SIS). These load factors, as shown in Table 1, represent a set of accelerations that encompass all of the launch vehicle configurations listed in the EELV SIS. The lateral and vertical directions listed in the table are relative to the launch vehicle coordinates. It should be noted that the lateral loads can be applied in any direction on the the ESPA cylinder. To account for this effect, the lateral quasi-static load factors are applied to ESPA in two directions. The first loading direction is when the lateral load is applied directly at a SPL. In the second case the lateral loading is directly between two of the SPLs. Thus, six load cases must be considered for the design of ESPA.

Table 1 Quasi-Static Load Factors Used in ESPA Design

Load Case	Acceleration Factors (Lateral, Vertical)	F.S.
1	(2.5, 3.5)	1.25
2	(1.5, 6.5)	1.25
3	(1.5, -2.0)	1.25

It should be noted that these loads may not be conservative for the design of some spacecraft. In order to get an accurate representation of the correct load factors for design, a dynamic coupled loads analysis

would have to be conducted for each particular spacecraft and launch vehicle configuration. However, since ESPA is designed to be a "generic" payload adapter, these details for every possible spacecraft/launch vehicle configuration can not be known. Therefore, ESPA is designed using very conservative assumptions and design margins. The first conservative assumption is that a PPL having a mass of 6800 kg (15,000 lb) and six 181 kg (400 lb) SPLs could be deployed on the ESPA ring. It would be unreasonable, given today's spacecraft densities to build a 181 kg (400 lb) spacecraft that would fit within the 61 cm x 61 cm x 97 cm (24 in x 24 in x 38-in) volume allotted. In addition, the heaviest PPL that could be deployed on ESPA with these 181 kg (400 lb) SPLs and still leave enough mass margin for fuel to be used for collision avoidance maneuvers is roughly 5400 kg (12000 lb). In addition, ESPA is designed to be very stiff so that its effect on the PPL is minimized. In fact, ESPA is a stiffness critical structure and given the current design, ESPA has a safety margin on strength of nearly 2.5.

4. ESPA FABRICATION PROCESS

The ESPA cylinder has been designed so that it can be machined from a single billet of aluminum. Using this approach, the entire ESPA structure, including Primary and Secondary Payload Mounting Flanges are integrally machined with the ESPA cylinder. This dramatically reduces the labor associated with bolting these flanges to the ESPA cylinder. It also greatly reduces the uncertainty, risk, part count, and lead-time associated with bolted or bonded joints. This design approach has reduced the cost of fabricating the ESPA structure from nearly \$300K to about \$75K when compared to a comparable design utilizing composite materials with bolted flanges.

The use of an integrally machined aluminum structure also precludes the necessity for acceptance testing of the structure. This results in an additional cost savings of over \$150K.

By designing the ESPA structure such that it can be integrally machined from a single aluminum billet will reduce the recurring cost by nearly \$450K and save nearly six months in lead-time compared to a similar design utilizing composite materials.

5. ESPA TESTING PROCEDURES

There are three objectives for testing the completed ESPA ring. These are: (1) Verify ESPA Stiffness, (2) Verify ESPA Strength Margins, and (3) Validate Modeling Procedures. To meet these objectives a dedicated qualification testing facility is being developed within AFRL/VS. This static testing facility, as shown in Figure 5, will allow each of the six load cases discussed in Section 3 to be applied to the ESPA ring. This computer controlled test system will allow up to 20 servo-hydraulic actuators to be simultaneously applied to the ESPA ring. 256 channels of strain and displacement data can be recorded during the test. The ESPA ring will be heavily instrumented during the qualification tests to provide both local strains and displacements. This information will be used to validate the ESPA ring strength margins, stiffness, and modeling procedures.

Figure 5 ESPA Static Testing Facility

Each of the six static load cases will be applied to the ESPA ring in four steps: (1) 25% Limit: Equipment Checkout, (2) 60% Limit: Verify Strain Predictions, (3) 110% Limit: Qual: Simulates Flight Article Load History, (4) 125% Limit: Qualification Load Level. There are no plans to test the ESPA ring to failure. The first three load cases can be applied to the ESPA ring in one configuration. To account for the direction of application of the radial forces, the load actuators will be rotated such that the line of action of the lateral forces falls between two of the SPLs. Thus, three load cases can be applied in one configuration, then the second three load cases will be applied in the second configuration.

Special adapters will be used between the ESPA ring and the static test frame. It would be optimal to use the actual adapters that ESPA will mate to during launch on the

EELV. The problem with this approach is that the Delta IV version of the EELV has a conical adapter fabricated using a composite sandwich configuration, while the Atlas V version of the EELV uses cylindrical aluminum adapters. Instead of conducting two separate qualification tests using two different adapters special adapters, nicknamed Mercury Adapters, or Hg Adapters, have been designed such that the stress state they produce envelopes the stress state in the ESPA ring when flown on these two different adapters. These Hg Adapters will be cylindrical adapters fabricated from aluminum billets.

6. REMAINING TECHNICAL CHALLENGES

The most challenging part of the development of the ESPA ring has been to design a truly generic structure that will accommodate the desires of future spacecraft designers. In this case, the spacecraft that will one day be deployed on the ESPA ring have yet to be conceived; furthermore, the development of the launch vehicle is not even finished. Therefore, this will probably remain the most challenging task of the ESPA development; to design a structure for which the requirements are not fully known.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The ESPA ring is well into the final stages of development. Qualification testing will begin in Spring 01 and a fully qualified ESPA should be available for flight by Fall 01.

The ESPA represents the first US capability to deploy up to six SPLs on an expendable launch vehicle. The ESPA promises to dramatically reduce the cost of access to space for small payloads; resulting in tremendous cost savings to the US Government and the US space industry.

Peter Wegner is a research engineer for the Air Force Research Laboratory's Space Vehicles Directorate. His research focuses on the design, fabrication, and testing of innovative structures for spacecraft and launch vehicle applications. He has a B.S. in Aerospace Engineering from the University of Arizona, a M.S. in Aerospace Engineering from Stanford University, and a Ph.D. in Mechanical Engineering from the University of Wyoming.

Jeff Ganley is a research engineer for the Air Force Research Laboratory's Space Vehicles Directorate. He works on the development of highly efficient structures for spacecraft and launch vehicles. He has a B.S. in Civil

Engineering from the University of Minnesota and a M.S. in Civil Engineering from the University of New Mexico.

Joseph Maly is a mechanical engineer at CSA Engineering, where he designs, analyzes, fabricates, and tests damping and isolation systems for aerospace structures. Currently, he is working on whole-spacecraft isolation for expendable launch vehicles, damping for the SOFIA airborne telescope system, and co-curing of viscoelastic materials with composites. He has a B.S. in Mechanical Engineering from the University of Cincinnati, and an M.S. in Applied Mechanics from Stanford University.